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TYPES OF NUCLEAR REACTORS AND METHODS OF TEACHING THEIR RADIATION SAFETY ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The article talks about the operation, types, and safety of nuclear reactors in the development of science and technology. That is, if we are able to convey nuclear power plants as safe energy in the mind of every growing young generation through pedagogical technologies, we can change the views regarding the innovation that is expected of us in the future. The article talks about the operation, types and safety of atomic reactors in the development of science and technology.

Keywords: Atomic, intensive, neutron, export, object, concept, strategy. Innovative, pedagogical, reactors.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, in our developing Uzbekistan, very successful work is being done in the field of energy. We can take nuclear energy as an example. One of the most urgent problems of today is the production of high-quality and low-cost energy. My main goal is to explain these problems to students using new pedagogical technologies through my article. Development is an integral part of any human activity. By gathering experience about nuclear reactors, improving methods and methods of action, and expanding his mental capabilities, man is constantly developing. The same process applies to any human activity, including pedagogy.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Nuclear reactors at various stages of development have introduced new standards and requirements for an increasingly new workforce. This required the development of the education system. One of the means of such development is innovative technologies, that is, radically new methods of interaction between teachers and students, which ensure effective results. Many talented scientists and teachers are involved in the problem of innovative technologies. Among them V.I. Andreev, I.P.

Podlasi, professor, doctor of pedagogic sciences K.K. Kolin, doctor of pedagogic sciences V.V. Shapkin, V.D. Simonenko, V.A. Slastenin and among them our Uzbek scientists Sodikov.I.I, Bozorov.E.H. All of them contributed immeasurably to the development. In innovative processes, Russia created modern nuclear technologies and caused radical changes in science. The research object of this is the process of developing long-term work education in a holistic way. The pedagogic system is currently trying to bring innovation through huge innovations and changes, and thus independent thinking in the minds of students, correct acceptance of the innovative changes that are currently taking place. and teaches to make wise decisions. Nuclear power plants are used in many countries in the world, and the use of pedagogical innovations for systematic analysis is the main prelude for the lessons to achieve their goals.

RESULTS

Pedagogical innovation is an innovation in the field of pedagogy, a purposeful progressive change that introduces, stable elements (innovations) that improve the educational environment, both of its individual components, and the specific characteristics of the educational system as a whole. Pedagogical innovations are carried out both at the expense of the educational system's own resources (through intensive development) and by attracting additional opportunities (investments) - new funds, equipment, technologies, capital investments, etc. can be increased (wide path of development). For the common man, modern high-tech devices are so mysterious that it is time to worship them like the ancient gods. High school physics classes filled with math won't solve the problem. But you can also learn interesting information about the nuclear reactor, the principle of its operation is interesting even for a teenager.

DISCUSSION

The Republic of Korea, which has few natural resources but is industrialized and overpopulated, is in dire need of energy. Against the background of Germany's abandonment of peaceful nuclear power, this country has high hopes for limiting nuclear technology: by 2035, the share of electricity produced by nuclear power plants is planned to increase to 60%, and the total production will exceed 40 gigawatts.

- Research in nuclear physics continues. Korean scientists have developed projects for modern reactors: modular, hydrogen, with liquid metal, etc.;
- The success of local researchers allows the technology to be sold abroad. In the next 15-20 years, the country is expected to export 80 of these products;
- But to date, most of the nuclear power plant has been built with the help of American or French scientists;

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the above-mentioned points, the use of pedagogical technologies in the teaching of atomic and nuclear energy contribute to the development of nuclear energy in our country.

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